

ON THE PREPARATION OF SULPHANILAMIDE DERIVATIVES. PART II. SULPHANILYLGUANIDINE

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A method has been described by which sulphanilylguanidine may be prepared by the action of ammonia on sulphanilyl cyanamide.

Sulphanilylguanidine (I) is considered to be a valuable antibacterial agent, particularly in the treatment of bacillary dysentery. It was first prepared by Buttle *et al* (*Biochem. J.*, 1938, 32, 1101) by heating *p*-aminobenzene sulphonamide with dicyandiamide. Subsequently, it has been prepared by the action of guanidine nitrate on acetyl sulphonyl chloride in acetone and subsequent hydrolysis of the reaction product (*cf. I.P.*, 28363):

The same acetyl sulphonyl chloride (II) reacts with isothiurea and the resulting condensation product on treatment with ammonia or any salt that liberates ammonia on heating, affords the acetylsulphanilylguanidine (II). This latter compound as usual undergoes hydrolysis to sulphaguanidine (*vide I.P.*, 29526). It has been subsequently noticed (*I.P.* 29613) that the isothiurea can be condensed with sodium salt of sulphanilamide in presence of phenol to give rise directly to sulphanilylguanidine.

While reacting the sodium salt of *p*-aminobenzene sulphonamide with alkyl sulphocyanides in phenolic medium to produce *o*-aminobenzene sulphocyanamide (III) (*cf. Part I* of the series), a guanidine derivative—sulphanilyl (*p*-sulphonamidophenyl) guanidine (IV), m.p. 216° shown in the experimental portion of the present paper, was isolated. The reaction proceeds as follows:

The formation of the above complex guanidine derivative (IV) by the interaction of the amino grouping of unreacted sulphanilamide with the cyano group of sulphanilyl cyanamide (III) indicated that the latter could readily undergo condensation with any

amine or ammoniacal bodies. This expectation has been fully realised by isolating sulphanilylguanidine itself from the above sulphanilyl cyanamide under the experimental conditions as described in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Sulphanilylguanidine

(i) A mixture of the sodium salt of *p*-aminobenzene sulphonyl cyanamide, m.p. 292° (7 parts), 7 parts of phenol and dry ammonium nitrate (2.5 parts) was heated at 180° for 1 hour. The mixture was diluted with benzene and the solid separating was collected and washed with dilute alkali. A solid that was left behind was crystallised from water in clusters of needles, m.p. 189°, after being dried at 100°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of sulphaguanidine showed no lowering. Solubility in water=250 mg. per 100 c.c., p_n of the solution so obtained=6.9, solubility in alcohol=600 mg. per 100 c.c. It forms hydrochloride, m.p. 205°. (Found : N, 26.25. $C_7H_{10}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 26.16 per cent.)

(ii) A mixture of the sodium salt of *p*-aminobenzene sulphonyl cyanamide, cresylic acid (7 parts) and dry ammonium nitrate (2.5 parts) was heated at 180° for 1 hour. By following the method as in (i), *p*-aminobenzene sulphonylguanidine was obtained as usual.

(iii) A stream of dry ammonia was passed while a mixture of the sodium salt of *p*-aminobenzene sulphonyl cyanamide (7 parts) and 7 parts of phenol was being gradually heated to 180°. The heating and passing of ammonia were continued for 1 hour at this temperature. The mixture was cooled and diluted with benzene. The solid was treated as in (i) and *p*-aminobenzene sulphonylguanidine was obtained.

(iv) *p*-Aminobenzene sulphonylguanidine was also obtained exactly in the same manner as in (iii) by using cresol instead of phenol as a solvent.

(v) The sodium salt of *p*-nitrobenzene sulphonamide (22.4 parts) was heated with 45 parts of phenol to 150°. To it was added ethyl sulphocyanide (8.7 parts) gradually with stirring. After 1 hour ammonium nitrate (8 parts) was added and the heating continued for 1 hour more at 180°. This was cooled and diluted with benzene. The solid that was obtained, was treated as in (i) when *p*-nitrobenzene sulphonylguanidine, m.p. 214° (with decomposition) was isolated. (Found : N, 23.1. $C_7H_8O_4N_2S$ requires N, 22.95 per cent). This nitro compound was reduced with iron and hydrochloric acid in the customary way and *p*-aminobenzene sulphonylguanidine isolated from the reaction mixture.

The sodium salt of *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphonamide (27 g.) was taken in 25 c.c. of phenol and heated to 140°. Ethyl sulphocyanide (10 g.) was then gradually added and the mixture heated for 1 hour at 150-160°. Ammonium nitrate (9 g.) was then added and the mixture refluxed for 2 hours more. This was cooled and diluted with benzene when a solid separated out. This was filtered and washed with dilute alkali and then crystallised from water when *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphonylguanidine, m.p. 263° separated in clusters of needles. (Found : N, 22.0. $C_9H_{10}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 21.28 per cent).

30 G. of the above compound and 150 c.c. of 5% hydrochloric acid were heated on a wire gauze for 35 minutes. It was cooled and made alkaline with dilute sodium hydroxide and the solid separating was crystallised from water, when *p*-aminobenzene sulphonylguanidine, m.p. 189° was obtained in clusters of needles.

Preparation of Sulphonamide-phenylsulphanilylguanidine.—The sodium salt of *p*-aminobenzene sulphonamide (9 parts) was taken in 18 parts of phenol and heated to 150°. Ethyl sulphocyanide (4 parts) was gradually added to the mixture and the heating continued for one hour more at 180°. The reaction mixture was cooled and diluted with benzene, filtered and the solid collected. The solid was dissolved in water and half neutralised with dilute hydrochloric acid when a solid separated out. This was purified by crystallisation from water (charcoal) in needle-shaped crystals, m.p. 216°. (Found: N, 18.84 C₁₃H₁₃O₄N₂S₂, requires N, 18.97 per cent).

This compound also separated out while preparing sulphanilyl cyanamide by reacting sodium salt of sulphanilamide with an alkyl sulphocyanide.

The paper is based on a pending patent application.

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